

NETWORK-CONNECTED PHOTOVOLTAIC INSTALLATION FOR ELECTRICITY PRODUCTION FOR THE TERRITORY OF SOFIA

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ABSTRACT. The article analyses the possibility of designing a photovoltaic power plant for a family house, which is connected to an existing low voltage / LV / electricity distribution network in Sofia with a capacity of 100 kWp, orientation 0°, gradient 30°, and with Si-poly photovoltaic modules. The PVSyst software was used. The most effective option for building the system was chosen: P50 from the three variants of the Poly 285 Wp 72 cells module offered - P50, P90, and P95. The time for investment return in years (pay-back) has been determined at the purchase price of the produced electricity: 0.40 BGN / kWh (fixed feed-in tariff).

Key words: grid connection, photovoltaic power plant, photovoltaic modules, investment, carbon emissions

МРЕЖОВОСВЪРЗАНА ФОТОВОЛТАИЧНА ИНСТАЛАЦИЯ ЗА ПРОИЗВОДСТВО НА ЕЛЕКТРОЕНЕРГИЯ ЗА ТЕРИТОРИЯТА НА ГР. СОФИЯ

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РЕЗЮМЕ. В статията се разглежда възможност за проектиране на фотоволтаична електроцентрала за фамилна къща, която е свързана към съществуваща електроразпределителна мрежа за ниско напрежение /НН/ на територията на гр. София с мощност 100 kWp, ориентация 0°, наклон 30° и с фотоволтаични модули Si-poly. Използван е програмния продукт PVSyst. Избран е най-ефективният вариант за изграждане на с-мата: P50 от предложените три разновидности на модула Poly 285 Wp 72 cells - P50, P90 и P95. Определено е времето за възвръщане на инвестицията в години (pay-back) при цена на изкупуване на произведената електрическа енергия: 0.40 лв. /kWh (fixed feed-in tariff).

Ключови думи: мрежово свързване, фотоволтаична електроцентрала, фотоволтаични модули, инвестиция, въглеродни емисии

Introduction

The continuing and deepening energy deficit of fossil fuels in the European countries, including Bulgaria, is growing. The economic dependence of the European states on the countries-exporters of oil, natural gas, and other deficient primary energy sources is increasing. The war in Ukraine has aggravated this problem. In this regard, the preparation of a new program for the development of renewable energy sources in Europe has begun. It envisages a sharp increase in the share of alternative and renewable sources in meeting the energy and fuel needs of the European countries. The Bulgarian domestic economic policy, which stimulates the development of the sector of naturally renewable energy sources is in line with the already existing and the new, even stricter, policy of limiting fossil non-ecological energy sources. Regardless of Europe's priority goal of creating competitive, sustainable, and secure power engineering, economic reasons are forcing the Bulgarian government to frequently change its regulations related to renewable energy sources, and seek to limit more expensive energy solutions, involving photovoltaic systems /PS/, despite their long-term beneficial effect (Law on Energy from Renewable Sources, effective from 05.07.2013).

In the present work, a photovoltaic on-grid power plant for a family house has been designed, which is connected to an existing low voltage electricity distribution network /LV/ on the territory of Sofia city with a power of 100 kWp, orientation 0°, gradient (slope) 30°, and with Si-poly photovoltaic modules (Vassilev Hr.et al., 2006). The PVSyst software product was used. The time for investment return in years (pay-back) at the purchase price of the produced electricity of has been determined: BGN 0.40 /kWh (fixed feed-in tariff) (Am Andonov et al., 2009).

Object of research

The object of research in the present development is a photovoltaic on-grid power plant, designed using the PVSyst software product ([http:// www.pvsyst.com](http://www.pvsyst.com)).

1. Nature

The photovoltaic power plant directly converts solar energy into electricity for general use, including for supplying electricity to the low voltage power network.

The photovoltaic converters of solar energy (photovoltaics, PV-panels) are made as elements with a certain area, and are called solar panels. They are elements that convert solar radiation directly into electricity and supply it to the conventional electricity distribution network (Koleva et al., 2003)

Photovoltaic systems form a significant and promising share of RES (renewable energy sources). The free, eco-friendly resource, the favourable regulations, and the incentive mechanisms applied for green technologies in more and more countries around the world are just some of the reasons why in the recent years, the PS have enjoyed increased investor interest, and their use is gradually becoming one of the most dynamically developing directions in the electric power engineering on a global scale.

2. Classification

PS allow classification by various indicators. Depending on the place of installation, the PS can be ground, roof, and built into the building facades, and according to the type of mounting structures - stationary and tracking (follow-up). Solar electrical installations can be autonomous and connected to the power network, and systematisation can be offered depending on their capacity. They are made of photovoltaic panels connected in parallel or in series ([http:// www.bzs-solar.de](http://www.bzs-solar.de)).

When connected in parallel, photovoltaics must have the same idling voltage and, more importantly, have the same voltage at the point of maximum capacity.

When connected in series, the photovoltaic panels must have the same characteristics. If this is not the case, the efficiency of the whole "string" is limited by the photovoltaic panel with lowest quality.

3. Production technologies

Currently, PV cells are produced by different technologies, as the efficiency and cost value of the modules vary depending on the material used and the specific conditions. Photovoltaics can be conditionally distinguished by first, second, and third generation technologies (Dechev, 2009).

The first group includes the silicon technologies, which are currently the most common and are characterised by the highest efficiency and price.

The second category of technologies uses photosensitive materials deposited as a very thin layer on a pad of cheap insulating material. They are characterised by a lower price, but are less effective and have a shorter life.

The third group includes concentrating PV technologies, organic photovoltaics, Grätzel cells, etc., which have not yet gained worldwide popularity.

Poly-crystalline silicon photovoltaic modules were used in the study (Koev, 2011; Velev, et al., 2012).

Concept for model research

The article considers the possibility of designing a photovoltaic on-grid power plant for a family house, which is connected to an existing low voltage /LV/ electricity distribution network in Sofia with a capacity of 100 kWp, orientation 0°, gradient 30°, and with Si-poly photovoltaic modules.

The PVsyst software was used. The time for return on investment in years will be determined at the purchase price of the produced electricity: 0.40 BGN / kWh.

The following parameters for project simulation /data/ are entered on the program setting screen: for the city of Sofia, capacity 100 kWp, orientation 0°, gradient 30°, photovoltaic modules Si-poly. Additionally, the following are set:

Price of modules: 1 BGN/Wp

Price of inverters: 2 BGN/kW

Other components:

Accessories – 3000 BGN

Cabling (wiring) - 7000 BGN

Training and analysis: Engineering - 3000 BGN

Installation of the plant:

Installation of modules - 10 BGN/module

Installation of inverters - 500 BGN/inverter

Connecting to the network - 10 BGN/kWp

Operating expenses:

Salaries - 24000 BGN/year

Financial parameters:

Own funds - 100000 BGN

Interest on the loan - 3%

It is possible to determine the time for investment return in years (pay-back) at the purchase price of the produced electricity : 0.40 BGN /kWh.

Results obtained

Project summary			
Geographical Site	Situation	Project settings	
Sofia	Latitude 42.70 °N	Albedo	0.20
Bulgaria	Longitude 23.32 °E		
	Altitude 559 m		
	Time zone UTC+2		
Meteo data			
Sofia			
Meteonorm 7.3 (1991-2000) - Synthetic			
System summary			
Grid-Connected System	No 3D scene defined, no shadings		
PV Field Orientation	Near Shadings	User's needs	
Fixed plane	No Shadings	Unlimited load (grid)	
Tilt/Azimuth	30 / 0 °		
System information			
PV Array		Inverters	
Nb. of modules	352 units	Nb. of units	1 Unit
Prom total	100 kWp	Prom total	100 kWac
		Prom ratio	1.003
Results summary			
Produced Energy	115.1 MWh/year	Specific production	1157 kWh/kWp/year
		Perf. Ratio PR	84.33 %
Table of contents			
Project and results summary	2		
General parameters, PV Array Characteristics, System losses	3		
Main results	4		
Loss diagram	5		
Special graphs	6		
P50 - P90 evaluation	7		
Cost of the system	8		
Financial analysis	9		

Fig.1. Input data and design content

Fig.2. Data on the connected photovoltaic modules / built PV system/

Fig.3. Losses in the system

Fig.4. Report on energy production

Fig.5. Annual main results by months

Fig.6. Report of losses from various factors Losses in the system /modules and inverter/

Fig.7. Project simulation parameters - dependence between average daily solar radiation and energy supplied to the network

Fig.8. Annual distribution of the output power of the system

Financial analysis			
Simulation period	20 years	Start year	2022
Income variation over time	0.00 %/year		
Production variation	0.00 %/year		
Discount rate	0.00 %/year		
Income dependent expenses	0.00 %/year		
Income tax rate	0.00 %/year		
Other income tax	0.00 %/year		
Dividends	0.00 %/year		
Financing			
Own funds	100000.00 BGN		
Loan	18540.00 BGN		
Electricity sale			
Feed-in tariff	0.40 BGN/kWh		
Duration of tariff warranty	20 years		
Annual connection tax	0.00 BGN/kWh		
Annual tariff variation	0.0 %/year		
Feed-in tariff decrease after warranty	50.00 %		
Return on investment			
Payback period	5.4 years		
Net present value (NPV)	323928.34 BGN		
Return on investment (ROI)	273.2 %		

Fig.11. Summary of the result for investment return

Fig.9. Probability distribution /when building the system with three variants of the module: P50, P90 and P95/

Detailed economic results (BGN)										
	Gross income	Loan principal	Loan interest	Run. costs	Deprec. allow.	Taxable income	Taxes	After-tax profit	Cumul. profit	%
2022	48438	690	556	24000	0	21881	0	21881	-7800	18.5%
2023	48438	711	536	24000	0	21902	0	21901	-5751	36.9%
2024	48438	732	514	24000	0	21920	0	21919	-3642	55.4%
2025	48438	754	492	24000	0	21945	0	21919	-15234	73.9%
2026	48438	777	470	24000	0	21968	0	21919	1507	92.5%
2027	48438	800	446	24000	0	21991	0	21919	27148	111.0%
2028	48438	824	422	24000	0	22016	0	21919	48340	129.9%
2029	48438	849	398	24000	0	22040	0	21919	69311	148.2%
2030	48438	874	372	24000	0	22065	0	21919	90723	168.9%
2031	48438	900	346	24000	0	22092	0	21919	111914	185.4%
2032	48438	927	319	24000	0	22119	0	21919	132108	204.1%
2033	48438	955	291	24000	0	22147	0	21919	152297	222.8%
2034	48438	984	262	24000	0	22175	0	21919	172488	241.5%
2035	48438	1013	233	24000	0	22205	0	21919	192680	260.2%
2036	48438	1044	203	24000	0	22236	0	21919	212871	279.0%
2037	48438	1075	171	24000	0	22266	0	21919	233053	297.9%
2038	48438	1107	139	24000	0	22299	0	21919	253234	316.6%
2039	48438	1140	106	24000	0	22332	0	21919	273418	335.4%
2040	48438	1175	72	24000	0	22366	0	21919	293597	354.3%
2041	48438	1210	36	24000	0	22401	0	21919	313769	373.2%
Total	928752	18540	6384	480000	0	442368	0	423928	323928	373.2%

Fig.12. Annual economic results - gross income, principle of loan, interest on the loan, current expenses, depreciation deductions, taxable income, taxes, profit after tax, Total profit / profitability / over the years

Cost of the system			
Installation costs			
Item	Quantity units	Cost BGN	Total BGN
PV modules			
Poly 255 Wp 72 cells	352	289.00	1007320.00
Inverters			
Central Inverter SOLVIA CM 100 EU G3	1	200.00	200.00
Studies and analysis			
Engineering	1	3000.00	3000.00
Installation			
Global installation cost per module	352	10.00	3520.00
Global installation cost per inverter	1	500.00	500.00
Accessories, fasteners	1	3000.00	3000.00
Wiring	1	7000.00	7000.00
Grid connection	1	1000.00	1000.00
Total			118540.00
Depreciable asset			118540.00
Operating costs			
Item			Total BGN/year
Maintenance			
Salaries			24000.00
Total (OPEX)			24000.00
System summary			
Total installation cost		118540.00 BGN	
Operating costs		24000.00 BGN/year	
Produced Energy		116 MWh/year	
Cost of produced energy (LCOE)		0.261 BGN/kWh	

Fig.10. Price of the system in BGN and annual production Financial analysis

Fig.13. Annual profits

Fig.14. Investment return

Conclusion

A photovoltaic on-grid electric power plant has been designed for a family house, which is connected to an already existing low voltage electricity distribution network /LV/ in Sofia. It is with a capacity of 100 kWp, orientation 0°, gradient 30°, and with Si-poly photovoltaic modules. The PVSyst software was used. The following conclusions were drawn:

- The network-connected photovoltaic power plant consists of 352 photovoltaic modules Poly 285 Wp 72 cells, arranged in 22 strings of 16 modules in a series. It is located on an area of 683 m²;

- The inverter is central: Central Inverter SOLIVIA CM 100 EU G3]

- From the performed calculations with the three proposed variants of the P50, P90, and P95 polycrystalline photovoltaic modules, the P50 module was chosen;

- The final price of the photovoltaic installation in the amount of BGN 323,828 thousand has been determined. With a service life of 20 years, the investments will be repaid after 5.4 years, and within the service life of the power plant will return by 273.2%;

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